

NOTES

2. H. A. MOHANTA and K. C. DASH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 166.
3. P. SINGH, G. P. POKHARIYAL and V. SINGH, *Acta Chim.* (Budapest) Accepted.
4. S. P. GHOSH and P. BHATTACHARJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 308.
5. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publication Inc., N. Y., 1962, p. 738.
6. A. D. LIEHR and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *Ann. Phys.*, 1959, 6, 134.
7. K. C. PATEL and D. E. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 637.
8. M. P. TEOTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chimica Acta*, 1973, 7, 340.
9. R. WALTON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 2229.
10. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand*, 1955, 9, 1362.
11. M. P. TEOTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chimica Acta*, 1973, 7, 343.
12. D. D. OZHA, K. N. KAUL and S. MEHTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1974, 43, 344.
13. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, R. L. GOBL, B. P. SINGH and R. P. MAHESH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 45, 137.

2-Hydroxy-4-Methylpropiophenone oxime as an Analytical Reagent : Studies on Nickel Complex

(Km.) L. C. JHAVERI, H. B. NAIK, G. S. PATEL
and
V. M. THAKOR*

Chemistry Department, M. R. Science Institute,
Gujarat College, Ahmedabad-380 006

Manuscript received 11 October 1976, revised 14 February
1980, accepted 31 March 1980

THE well known reagents for gravimetric determination of nickel are dimethylglyoxime¹, nioxime², resacetophenone oxime³. 2-Hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone oxime⁴, 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone oxime⁵ and 5-ethylresacetophenone oxime⁶ have been used as analytical reagents for nickel. In a project designed to develop new organic reagents for the determination of metal ions the use of 2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone oxime has been investigated as a gravimetric reagent for Ni(II). An ethanolic solution of the reagent reacts with Ni(II) quantitatively forming a green complex of 1:2 stoichiometry analysing for Ni(C₁₀H₁₂O₂N)₂. The Ni(II) complex is insoluble in hot water and hot aq. ethanol (60–70% v/v). The complex can be dried without decomposition at 110–20° and is directly weighable as Ni(C₁₀H₁₂O₂N)₂. Cations like aluminium(III), cadmium(II), lead(II), zinc(II), mercury(II), barium(II), calcium(II), manganese(II), cobalt(II), magnesium(II) and anions like

tartrate, citrate, chloride, nitrate are found not to interfere at pH range 5.0 to 5.5. Interference of Fe(III) was removed by masking with sodium potassium tartrate before adding the reagent. Gravimetric determination of copper and nickel in their binary mixture has been carried out with satisfactory results taking advantage of the different pH range for precipitation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Stock solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving pure salts in double distilled water and were employed after standardisation by standard methods.

Ammonium hydroxide and acetic acid were used to prepare buffers of different pH values.

Reagent : 2-Hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone Oxime :

2-Hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone⁷ was obtained in almost quantitative yield by Fries migration of m-cresyl propionate⁸ in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Its oxime⁷ was prepared by refluxing its alcoholic solution with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide (40%). It was purified by repeated crystallisation from petroleum, m.p. 104°.

Gravimetric estimation of Ni(II) : An aliquot of standard solution of Ni(II) containing 6 to 20 mg of Ni(II) was diluted to 150 ml and pH was adjusted to 5.5 using ammonia and acetic acid buffer. The contents were heated to 60–70° and treated with 1% ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone oxime added dropwise with constant stirring (about twice the theoretical amount). The green precipitate obtained was digested on a water-bath for 30 min and filtered through a G-4 sintered glass crucible. It was washed with hot water several times and finally with 60% ethanol and dried at 110–20° to a constant weight. It has been found that the precipitation of nickel is quantitative in the pH range 5.0–10.0. The conversion factor (nickel/nickel complex) is 0.1416. Some representative results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Ni(II)

Ni(II) taken (mg)	Ni(II) found (mg)	Error (%)
5.94	5.92	-0.34
11.88	11.85 11.82	-0.25 -0.51
14.85	14.87 14.85	+0.13 ±0.00
20.79	20.81 20.85	+0.096 +0.29
29.70	29.8	+0.34

Present address : *H. & H. B. Kotak Institute of Science,
Rajkot.

Precision and accuracy: The relative standard deviation in the determination of nickel (14.85 mg) by the given method was $\pm 0.4\%$ in 20 determinations.

Determination of nickel in the presence of other ions: The procedure was the same as in the absence of foreign ions. The interference in some cases was removed by working at low pH to prevent the precipitation of corresponding hydroxides. Interference due to Fe(III) was removed by adding potassium tartrate. By suitable adjustment of pH, a number of cations and anions could be tolerated e.g., Ca(II) and Ba(II) (about 20 times), Al(III), Cd(II), Pb(II), Zn(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Co(II), (about 2 to 3 times), Mg(II) (about 10 times), large amount of tartrate, citrate, chloride and nitrate could be tolerated at pH 5.0 to 5.5.

From the solution containing both copper and nickel, copper was first precipitated and estimated at pH 3.0 as reported⁹ earlier and from the filtrate nickel was precipitated by addition of more reagent and adjustment of pH 5.0 to 5.5 as indicated above. The results are reproducible with an error $\pm 0.4\%$ for amounts of Ni(II) ranging from 2.97 to 15.0 mg. The reagent is readily prepared and less expensive.

Composition of the complex: The nickel complex was analysed to determine the composition. (Found: Ni, 13.68; N, 6.62, Calc: Ni, 14.16; N, 6.75%). The molecular weight determined cryoscopically using camphor as solvent showed the complex to be monomeric, i.e., the complex could be represented by ML_2 . The 1:2 composition of the complex was confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation, potentiometric and conductometric studies. The formula of the complex may therefore be represented as $Ni(C_{10}H_{14}O_2N)_2$. The complex can be extracted in benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride.

Examination of the IR spectrum of the reagent showed strong bands at 3400 cm^{-1} (ν OH chelated), 2980 cm^{-1} (ν OH of $=N-OH$), 1640 cm^{-1} (ν C=N), 980 cm^{-1} (ν N-O) and 790 cm^{-1} (1,2,4 trisubstituted benzene). Examination of the IR spectrum of the chelate shows that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the metal because the band at 2980 cm^{-1} due to hydroxy group of the oximino moiety appears more or less at the same position in both the ligand and the complex and 3400 cm^{-1} peak of the chelated OH disappears in the complex. In the chelate the band at 1640 cm^{-1} disappears and a stronger band appears at 1610 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to C=N shifting down field, due to complexation.

The UV and visible spectra were mapped using solution of this complex in chloroform and peaks at 300 nm, 375 nm and 600 nm were obtained. The magnetic susceptibility of this chelate showed that it is diamagnetic in character.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Principal, Gujarat College, Ahmedabad for providing research facilities.

Thanks are due to S. P. University, Vallabh-Vidyanagar for UV and visible spectra and Cadila Laboratories, Ahmedabad for IR spectra.

References

1. L. TSCHUGAEFF. *Ber. dt. Chem. Ges.*, 1905, 38, 2520.
2. R.C. VOTER, C.V. BANKS and H. DIEHL, *Analyst. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 459.
3. K. S. BHATKI and M. B. KABADI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 346.
4. S. PRAKASH, Y. DUTT and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 664.
5. L. C. JHAVERI, G. S. PATEL and V. M. THAKOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 730.
6. N. D. NAIK, H. B. NAIK and C. M. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 405.
7. C. E. COULTHAND, J. MARSHALL and F. L. PYMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280.
8. R. BALTZLY and A. BASS *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4292.
9. L. C. JHAVERI, G. S. PATEL and V.M. THAKOR, *Chemical Era*, 1976, 11, 29.

Effect of UV Light on Aqueous Solution of Tartaric Acid in the Presence of Nitrogen under Heterogeneous Conditions

K. S. KHETWAL

Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University,
Naini Tal, U. P. India

Manuscript received 14 June 1979, accepted 31 March 1980

SYNTHESIS of specific life forming molecules is at present being investigated under conditions believed to have existed in the pre-biological era of earth. The problem of abiotic synthesis of such compounds has been discussed by a number of workers i. e., Oparin, Haldane, Miller, Ponnampereuma and others¹⁻⁹. They have emphasised that the molecules that are fundamental today were fundamental at the time of abiogenesis of living matter. It has been suggested that in the ancient abiotic periods of earth, diverse types of organic compounds would have been formed by various methods which would not have required any kind of living or vital forces. Tartaric acid one of such compounds under nitrogen atmosphere was irradiated by ultraviolet light with a view to see the formation of life forming molecules.

It is well known that tartaric acid in aqueous solution decomposes rapidly when exposed to UV light giving a variety of products¹⁰⁻¹². However, the action of UV light on aqueous solution of tartaric acid under nitrogen atmosphere has not yet been studied. Therefore, it was considered of interest and the effect of UV light on aqueous solutions of tartaric acid in the